

Sustainable Development of Industries Through Safety, Productivity, Economic & Working Environments

1. Sreerama Meraka (*Corresponding Author*), Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering Department, Raghu Engineering College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

2. G.Venu madhav, Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering Department, Raghu Engineering College, Visakhapatnam, India

3. Raghavendra Yeddu, Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering Department, Raghu Engineering College, Visakhapatnam, India

4. K. Sureshbabu, Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering Department, Raghu Engineering College, Visakhapatnam, India

Received: Dec 8, 2025

Accepted: Jan 5, 2025

Published: Jan 7, 2026

Abstract:

The meaning of sustainability is comprehensive and could include so many factors. Especially for industrial sector to adopt sustainability is a difficult task. Sustainability is an inexorably pertinent issue in all nations for building a cleaner, greener and prosperous industry around the globe. Sustainable Development of Industries is possible through safety, productivity, economic & working environments. Industrial sickness is one of the negative impacts on sustainability. "sick industries" refers to companies that are facing financial distress and potential closure. These companies often experience accumulated losses exceeding their net worth, leading to a state of sickness. This paper explores the insights and root causes for industrial sickness, and suggests a constructive framework towards sustainable development.

Key Words: Sustainability, Productivity, Sick industries, Working Environments, Financial distress.

1.1 Introduction

The human wants have not been confined to the psychological needs like food, clothing and shelter but human beings also aspire for the status, recognition, esteem. The human civilization has passed through the varied stages with settled life, village society or household system, handicraft system, factory system, industrial town and city life, global partnership stage.

1.2 Major Stages of Economy Growth:

The economic development of the human being can broadly be classified into following two stages :

1. Pre-Industrial Revolution Era.
2. Modern Industrial Era.

Pre- Industrial Revolution Era: The economic and business life human beings under pre industrial era can be classified chronologically as under

- Self sufficient stage
- Commercial stage with marketable surplus
- Barter system
- Money system

Development of means of transportation

Modern Industrial Era had its root in the industrial revolution. Many other factors subsequently contributed to the growth and development of modern industrial world. Broadly speaking the technological revolutions took place in the following stages:

- Industrial Revolution
- Development of corporate form of the organization
- Managerial Revolution
- Technological Development.

2. History and Development of Indian Industry:

In the 16 th and 17 th century india was well known for crafts, industrie like marble work, stone carving, wood carving, jewellery, brass and copper metal wares. Textile handicrafts was the major industry. It was spread all over the country. During that period indias exports to Europe consisted of cotton and silk fabricks, aristic wares, silk and woolen clothes.. It also included spices such as paper , cinnamon, cloves and other products.

Then came the long period of rule by East india Company (1757-1858) and the British government(1858-1947) which exploited Indians resources by all possible means.

Government of India Initiate Industrial Policy: Government of india recognize the need of industrialization for growth of a nation. and make special industrial policy for development.

Industrial Policy Resolution 1948: In April 1948, Govt.of India announced its industrial policy resolution as a first step towards a sound industrial policy.

Industries (Development and Regulation) Act,1951: This act establish central advisory council and Development.Councils.

New Industrial Policy Resolution ,1956: In 1956 when india started second five year plan, Government announced the new industrial policy Resolution.

3. Sick Industries:

In India, "sick industries" refers to companies that are facing financial distress and potential closure. These companies often experience accumulated losses exceeding their net worth, leading to a state of sickness. Several factors, including outdated technology, poor management, and economic downturns, can contribute to industrial sickness.

3.1 According to Government agencies Definition:

- Sick Industrial Companies (Special Provisions) Act, 1985 (SICA): This act defined a sick industrial company as one registered for at least 5 years that has accumulated losses equal to or exceeding its entire net worth.
 - Reserve Bank of India (RBI): RBI defines a sick unit as one that has incurred cash losses for one year and is likely to continue incurring losses, with an imbalance in its financial structure.
 - State Bank of India (SBI): SBI defines a sick unit as one that fails to generate adequate returns.
- Examples of Sick Industries:

3.2 Some of the Sick industries information with the Root Cause of Sickness:

S.No	Type of Industrial Unit	Root Cause for Sickness
1.	Hindustan Cables Limited (HCL)	A public sector company that became sick due to outdated technology, high costs, and low demand.
2.	HMT Ltd (Hindustan Machine Tools)	Faced losses due to outdated products and competition.
3.	Scooters India Ltd (SIL)	Suffered from poor management and low demand.
4.	Kingfisher Airlines	A service sector example with huge losses due to financial mismanagement and rising costs.
5.	National Textile Corporation (NTC)	Many mills under NTC became sick due to rising costs and outdated machinery. Causes of Industrial Sickness
6.	.Birds Jute & Exports Ltd	Increased competition, changes in government policies
7.	Indian Oil –creda biofuels Ltd.	Inadequate financial planning, changes in government policies

8.	South –central east Delhi power transmission	Qver-capitalization, lack of innovation, inadequate financial planning
9.	HMT Watches Ltd.	Outdated machinery, Increased competition
10.	Hindustan Fertilizers corporation Ltd.	Financial mismanagement and rising costs

Table- 1

3 .3 Impact of Industrial Sickness:

- Loss of jobs, wastage of national resources, and social unrest.
- Impact on creditors, investors, and the overall economy.

4. The Suggested Key Factors (Frame work) for over come to Industrial Sickness:

3.1 Safety in Industry: From 1912 to the present time, remarkable advances have been made in reducing the rate and severity of accidents.

The importance of industrial safety was realized because every year millions of industrial accidents occur which result in either or temporary and permanent disablement of the employees and involve a good amount of cost such as resulting from wasted manhours, machine hours etc.

Need for safety: Safety plays a vital role for Sustainability of industries . Safety in industries helps,

- Increasing rate of production
- Reducing production cost
- Reducing damage to equipment and machinery
- Preventing premature death of talented workers who are an asset to the society.

3.2 Productivity: Productivity it is another important factor to influence Sustainability of industries. It is aimed at to raise the productivity within the available resources.

It is defined as the ratio between output and input. Output means the amount produced or the number of items produced and input are the various resources employed like land and building, equipment and machinery , materials, labour,etc.

Better Productivity can achieve:

- Making earnings
- To clear the debts or loans acquired from different sources.
- To stand better in the market.
- Promote better working conditions
- Create job security and satisfaction among workers

3.3 Working, Environmental Conditions:

Human work behavior to a great extent can be influenced by the working environments or Working conditions.

- Working conditions of physical nature, e.g Illumination(Lighting), Heating, Ventilating, Air –Conditioning, Noise, etc

Improper working conditions of physical nature increase fatigue and reduce output and product quality.

- Working conditions related to time, e.g Hours of work(8- hours day and 40 – hours week are probably best in terms of efficiency and absenteeism)

Rest pauses . Rest pauses such as tea and coffee breaks or otherwise are necessary to prevent excessive physiological and mental fatigue.

- Working conditions related to social situation within which individual work, e.g
- Community attitude towards the objective of the organization.
- Acceptance of company employees by the community.
- Social welfare etc..

4. Various Banks, Government Agencies for Providing Financial Assistance to Sustainable Development of Industries

S.No	Name of the Bank / Agency	Nature of Assistance
1.	Department of Public Enterprises & Industrial Reconstruction (PE & IR)	To provide necessary capital for sick industries in terms of raising capital, Infrastructure, Machinery.
2.	Industrial Development Bank of India(IDBI)	Exclusive Bank for industrial development. To provide necessary capital for sick industries in terms of raising capital, Infrastructure, Machinery
3.	Industrial Credit & Investment Corporation of India(ICICI)	Exclusive Bank for industrial development. To provide necessary capital for sick industries in terms of raising capital, Infrastructure, Machinery
	Small Industries Development Bank of India(SIDBI)	To provide Necessary Capital
	Andhra Pradesh industrial Infrastructure Corporation(APIIC)	To provide Infrastructure, Machinery.

Table-2

Conclusion: Sustainability is a way of practice to build a good industrial Sector. There are so many key factors to suggests for Industrialists and Entrepreneurs, how to construct a frame work towards sustainable development of industries.

References:

{1 } **Industrial Engineering and management by –O.P. .Khanna**

{2Industrial Engineering and Production Management- M.Mahajan

[3] <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/10.1504/IJISE.2023.129133>

[4] <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/sustainable-food-systems/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2022.1034010/full>

[5] <https://ijirem.org/DOC/18-a-study-on-industrial-sickness-concept-and-causes.pdf>